

A Comparative Study of Functional Outcome of Cemented Vs Uncemented Bipolar Hemiarthroplasty for Intracapsular Femur Neck Fractures In Patients above 60years of Age

Umer Hamdan¹, Ashok V Bangarashettar², Manu Patel M.D.³, Prashant Kumar⁴

¹Junior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Karnataka Institute of Medical Sciences, Hubli, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Karnataka Institute of Medical Sciences, Hubli, India

³Junior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Karnataka Institute of Medical Sciences, Hubli, India

⁴Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Karnataka Institute of Medical Sciences, Hubli, India

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Manu Patel M.D

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Intracapsular fracture neck femur account for a major share of fractures in the elderly. The primary goal of treatment is to return the patient to their pre-fracture functional status. Hemiarthroplasty has been considered the treatment of choice in femur neck fractures in elderly. This study plans to compare the safety, effectiveness and clinical results of cemented and uncemented bipolar hemiarthroplasty in treating fracture neck of femur in patients aged >60yrs of age.

Methodology: The present comparative study includes 30 cases of intracapsular fracture neck of femur in elderly aged more than 60y, who were divided into 2 groups with 15 patients in each group; the groups were being assigned based on Dorr's Index. One group was treated by hemiarthroplasty using uncemented prosthesis whereas the other group was treated with hemiarthroplasty using cemented prosthesis. Patients were followed up for 6 months and functional outcome was assessed at the end of this period.

Results: There was no statistical difference in the functional outcome between the two groups in our study ($p=0.53$). Despite the known physiological effect of cement upon the cardiopulmonary system, we found no clinical morbidity or mortality because of this in our study. Surgical time (80.66minutes versus 31.53 minutes) and blood loss (281.33ml versus 226.66ml) was statistically significant for the cemented cohort than the uncemented ($P<0.001$). Post-operative pain after 6weeks was less in the cemented group ($p=0.013$)

Conclusion: In femur neck fractures, both the cemented and uncemented bipolar prosthesis have a similar functional outcome in our study. Although the operative time and blood loss was higher in the cemented group, post-operative pain was less. We suggest both the types of hemiarthroplasties as good treatment options for treatment of femoral neck fractures in elderly.

Keywords: Fracture neck of femur, Cemented hemiarthroplasty, uncemented hemiarthroplasty, Harris Hip Score, Elderly.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Femoral neck fracture is a most common injury which can lead to increased postoperative morbidity and mortality in elderly patients. As health care costs increase, evaluating treatment methods in femoral neck fractures to determine the most effective treatment paradigm will become increasingly important. Management of displaced intracapsular hip fracture in elderly remains controversial. Hemiarthroplasty, as an effective treatment, [1] contributes to early ambulation and good functional recovery. However, there has been persistent controversy over whether cemented hemiarthroplasty (CH) or uncemented hemiarthroplasty (UCH) is preferable for the patient population. An arthroplasty using a

cemented implant may be associated with increased mortality compared with an arthroplasty using an uncemented implant. Cementation of the prosthesis achieves good initial fix in an osteoporotic bone, however arthroplasty using a cemented implant may be associated with increased mortality compared with an arthroplasty using an uncemented implant, as it has the risk of bone marrow and fat embolization with resulting intraoperative hypotension and increased incidence of deep vein thrombosis. The mechanisms involved are not fully understood but involve cardiorespiratory disturbances caused by venous and pulmonary embolization of bone marrow contents and methyl methacrylate particles. [2,3,4]

An uncemented implant may be associated with design-specific complications such as stress shielding, thigh pain, and a higher risk of periprosthetic fracture. This may be the result of the inferior method of fixation or the design of the prosthesis.

Hemiarthroplasty is the most common treatment for displaced fractures of the femoral neck in the elderly [1,5] and is associated with better functional outcome and fewer reoperations than internal fixation. [3,4] A large number of prostheses have been used, and no definite conclusions have been made regarding which type of arthroplasty is preferred. [2,5]

Whether a specific type of hemiarthroplasty using an uncemented implant could yield the same clinical results as a hemiarthroplasty using a cemented implant for treatment of displaced femoral neck fractures is unclear.

Whether a Bipolar hemiarthroplasty using an uncemented implant could yield the same clinical results as a Bipolar hemiarthroplasty using a cemented implant for treatment of displaced femoral neck fractures is still unclear. It is therefore planned to compare the effectiveness and safety of cemented bipolar hemiarthroplasty and uncemented bipolar hemiarthroplasty in treating femoral neck fractures in elderly patients.

This in-depth evaluation will provide valuable information and more accurate evidences for surgeons in making a clinical decision.

Methods and Material

The present comparative study includes 30 cases of intracapsular fracture neck of femur in elderly aged more than 60y, who were divided into 2 groups with 15 patients in each group, the groups were being assigned based on cortical index and Dorr's Index. One group of the patients was treated by hemiarthroplasty using uncemented bipolar prosthesis whereas the other group was treated with hemiarthroplasty using cemented bipolar prosthesis.

The study is conducted in the department of Orthopaedics at Karnataka Institute of Medical Sciences, Hubli, Karnataka over a period of 18 months from February 2021 to July 2022. The Ethical clearance has been obtained from ethical committee.

The study has been carried out to study the advantages, complications, Postoperative pain and functional outcome in each of the procedure and to draw a conclusion based on study results as to which type of fixation would be better in the management of fracture neck of femur in elderly.

Source of Data: Data is collected from patients presenting with symptoms of fracture neck femur

Karnataka Institute of Medical Sciences, Hubli, Karnataka.

Method of Collection of Data

After obtaining institutional ethics committee clearance and written informed consent, the in-patients in the Department of Orthopaedics, KIMS Hubli, fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria will be enrolled in the study. Each patient will be given a unique identity number. Demographic data, medical history, concomitant medications, physical examination, clinical examination including recording of vital signs and details of the implant used by the treating doctor will be recorded in the study proforma and relevant radiological investigations as mentioned in the assessment tools will be done at baseline visit.

Follow-up visits will be at 2 weeks (visit 1), 6 weeks (visit2) and 24 weeks (visit 3) from the date of surgery. A deviation of ± 2 days for first follow-up and ± 1 week for subsequent follow-ups will be accepted. At follow-up visits, presenting complaints, general physical examination, local examination of the affected hip and standard radiographs will be recorded.

A Functional score will be obtained using Harris Hip (Annexure 1) score at these visits and pain assessment done using a Visual Analogue Scale. (Annexure 2)

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients with age group >60 yrs of either sex.
2. Radiological evidence of intra capsular fracture neck of femur.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients <60 yrs of age.
2. Pathological fractures.
3. Polytrauma patients.
4. Unable to walk before fracture

Surgical Procedure: All surgeries were performed on an elective basis using standard aseptic precautions surgery was performed under spinal or general anesthesia.

All the patients were operated in lateral position through the posterior approach.

Clinical Evaluation: Clinical evaluation is done based on Harris Hip Score.

Assessment of Pain: All the follow up patients were Assessed for pain at the intervals of 2weeks, 6weeks and 6months post op using Visual Analogue Scale and the ratings were recorded.

Results

In this study, 30 elderly patients with displaced femoral neck fractures were treated surgically with hemiarthroplasty at KIMS, Hubli. Of the 30 pa-

tients, 15 patients had cemented bipolar prosthesis hemireplacement and the other 15 had uncemented bipolar prosthesis hemireplacement. Patients were included in either group based on Dorr's Index and intra operative assessment. The following observations were made from the data collected.

Age Incidence: The average age of the patients in our series is 74.26 years, with mean age of 74.40 years in males and 73.63 years in females.

Sex Incidence: In our series there were 20 female patients and 10 male patients. This shows preponderance of females over male patients.

No of male: 4 Uncemented + 6 Cemented = 10 (32.5%)

No of female: 11 Uncemented + 9 Cemented = 20 (67.5%)

Side Involved

Out of 30 cases 16 cases (53.33%) were on the left side and 14 cases (46.66%) are on the right. Uncemented: R- 7/ L-8 = 15 Cemented: R- 7/ L-8= 15

Mechanism of Injury: Majority (96.66%) of the patients had minimal trauma most of them slipped and fell down on flat ground or in bathroom and were not able to walk or stand. Only one patient was involved in road traffic accident. Fall: 96.66%, Road traffic accident: 3.33%

Associated Medical and Surgical Problems: Associated disorders like Diabetes Mellitus, Hypertension, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease,

Cerebrovascular Accident, Ischemic Heart Disease, Anemia, were present in about 11 cases (36.66%).

These patients were evaluated and treated by physician in the early period of hospitalization. The patients were taken up for surgery only after they became medically fit for the surgical procedure.

Complications

The complications were distributed in both groups. In the cemented group we had one case (6.66%) of prosthesis dislocation postoperatively; for which closed reduction under general anesthesia along with an adductor tenotomy was done. One case (6.66%) of deep infection which responded to wound debridement and IV antibiotics with regular dressing, one case of bed sore which was superficial grade 1 and one case of superficial infection which responded to antibiotics and regular dressing were noted. In the uncemented group we had one case of superficial infection which responded to antibiotics and regular dressing and one case of bed sore which was superficial grade 1.

Duration of Surgery (In Mins) and Blood Loss

(In ml): In the uncemented group the mean duration of surgery was 80.66 minutes with a mean amount of blood loss of 226.66 milliliters, whereas in the cemented group the mean duration of surgery was 91.53 minutes and mean amount of blood loss being 281.33 milliliters. Surgical time (91.53 minutes versus 80.66minutes) and blood loss (281.33ml versus 226.66 ml) was greater for the cemented cohort than the uncemented. The difference between the groups was significant ($P < 0.001$).

Table 1: Amount of blood loss and duration of surgery

Prosthesis	Results	
	Amount of blood loss in ml	Duration of surgery in mins
Uncemented	226.66	80.66
Cemented	281.33	91.53
P value	<0.001 statistically significant	

Assessment of Functional Results Using Harris Hip Score

The assessment was done as per the Harris Hip Scoring system under the following headings and the assessment was done at 2weeks, 6weeks and 6months post op.

Mean Harris Hip Score at 2 weeks: The mean Harris Hip Score at 2 weeks for the uncemented group was 64.6 and for the cemented group was 66.66. This was not statistically significant.

Mean Harris Hip Score at 6 weeks:

The mean Harris Hip Score at 6 weeks for the uncemented group was 74.73 and for the cemented group were 75.06. This was not statistically significant.

Mean Harris Hip Score at 6 months:

The mean Harris Hip Score at 6 months for the uncemented group was 84.86 and for the cemented group were 86.13. This was not statistically significant.

Table 2: Mean Harris Hip Score at 6 months

HHS	
Uncemented	84.86
Cemented	86.13
P value	0.533

Harris Hip Score outcome at the end of 6 months: In the Uncemented group: 4 patients had excellent outcome, 9 patients had Good outcome and 2 patients had Fair outcome. In the Cemented group: 5 patients had excellent outcome, 9 patients had Good outcome and 1 patient had a poor outcome.

Table 3: Outcome based on Harris Hip Score

Prosthesis	Outcome based on Harris Hip Score			
	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor
Uncemented	4	9	2	0
Cemented	5	9	0	1

Visual Analogue Score at 2 weeks: The mean Visual Analogue Score at 2 weeks for the uncemented group was 3.466 and for the cemented group were 3.133. This was not statistically significant.

Visual Analogue Score at 6 weeks: The mean Visual Analogue Score at 6 weeks for the

uncemented group was 3.2 and for the cemented group were 2.8. This was statistically significant.

Visual Analogue Score at 6 months: The mean Visual Analogue Score at 6 months for the uncemented group was 2.46 and for the cemented group was 1.866. This was statistically significant.

Table 4: Mean VAS at 6 months

Mean VAS	
Uncemented	2.466
Cemented	1.866
P Value	0.004 - statistically significant

Discussion

Femoral neck fractures are common injuries among elderly people [6]. The most common treatment for a displaced femoral neck fracture in the elderly is hemiarthroplasty. The hemiarthroplasty is either cemented into the femoral canal or uncemented with press-fit technique [7]. The question of whether a hemiarthroplasty should be cemented has been a topic of controversy and on-going debate until present. The most common fixation method of the femoral stem has been cementing with special bone cement. However, this method has some disadvantages. The duration of surgery is longer than in uncemented technique. Also, blood loss is greater and there is a risk of sudden death at the time of cementing. There is a long-standing debate

on the superiority of the two methods [7]. In this context we undertook the present study to evaluate and compare the complications and functional outcome of a uncemented bipolar hemiarthroplasty with cemented bipolar hemiarthroplasty in a population >60years of age.

The results were analyzed and observations were made. This study was compared to the similar studies by other authors.

Age Incidence

The average age incidence in our study was 74.26 years with a range of 68 to 85 years with majority of the patients coming under the age group of 71-80years. Our study was comparable to other studies as mentioned in the table.

Table 5: Mean ages in years, in various comparable clinical studies

Clinical Studies	Mean Age In Years
Our study	74.26y
Jaimo Ahn MD, PhD, Li-Xing Man MD et.al,	78y
R.J.K. Khan et.al,	83y
Wender Figved MD, et.al,	70y

Sex Incidence

In our series the intracapsular fracture of femoral neck were found to be more common in females 20 of 30 patients (66.66%). The elderly females are

more prone to fracture neck of femur due to osteoporosis [8].

Female preponderance has been reported in several series Moore [9] 1957: 62.5%, Campbell (1960):

80.9%; Cone (1963): 73.6%; Anderson & Neilson (1972): 85%.

Nature of Injury

Majority (93.33%) of the patients had minimal trauma most of them having history of slip and fall while walking. This is in accordance with majority of the series reported – Gyepes [10] (1962), Solomon (1968), Evarts [11] (1973), Fielding [12] (1974), Ingalhalikar [13] (1987), Seth [14] (1987), Stevens et al. [15] (1962), Scott and Gray (1980).

Associated Medical Conditions

The common problems in our series were hypertension, diabetes mellitus and ischemic heart disease. 12 cases i.e., 40% of our patients had one or more of the problems. Hypertension (20%) and Diabetes (13.33%) were the major problems in our study. 2 patients (6.66%) had ischemic heart diseases in our series. Hypertension, diabetes mellitus was commonly detected after the patient got admitted with fracture neck of femur. Patients with nervous system disorder and mental problems are not found in our series whereas they were common in western series.

Complications

1. Periprosthetic Fracture

In our study we had no cases of periprosthetic fractures. Hinchey and Day (1964) emphasize that all Periprosthetic fractures occur when the surgeon attempts to reduce the prosthesis [16]. R.J.K. Khan et al. [17] reported three iatrogenic periprosthetic fractures, all occurring in the uncemented group. Foster et al. [18] in 2005 from Northern Ireland [15], in their retrospective analysis of 244 patients of which 70 patients had uncemented prosthesis, 7% (5/70) of patients with uncemented prosthesis suffered a periprosthetic fracture. Wender Figved

MD et al [19] reported Intraoperative periprosthetic fracture one case (0.9%) in cemented group & 2(1.9%) in uncemented groups.

2. Dislocation

In our study we had one case of dislocation (3.33%) in cemented group which was found on the 3 weeks Post op. The dislocation was successfully reduced under general anaesthesia. Jameson et al. [20] reported higher dislocation rate in the cemented group (0.44% vs. 0.25%). Wender Figved MD et al [19] reported 5 cases of dislocation in each cemented (4.5%) & uncemented (4.6%) groups.

3. Deep Vein Thrombosis

There were no cases of clinically detectable deep vein thrombosis noted in the study period. Our results matched with similar studies like Wender Figved MD et al. [19] Jaimo Ahn MD et al. [19] who reported zero cases of clinically detectable DVT.

4. Infections

In our study we had one (3.33%) superficial infection in the uncemented group and one case (3.33%) of superficial infection in the cemented group. Wender Figved MD et al. [19] only one case of superficial infection (0.9%) in the cemented group. One case (3.33%) of deep infection was noted in our study.

Superficial infection was seen in the 2 patients in our study. They developed signs of infection in the first week of operation. They were treated with proper antibiotics and dressings. All these infections were found when the patients were still in the hospital and this resulted in prolongation of their hospital stay.

Figure 1: Superficial Skin Infection

5. Bed Sore

In our study we had one (3.33%) case of bed sore in the uncemented group and one (3.33%) case of bed sore in the cemented group. In both the groups the bed sore were seen in patients with prolonged immobilization secondary to conditions like delay in surgery due to comorbidities like diabetes, anemia and postoperative immobilization. The bed sores responded to regular dressing and pressure reducing measures like regular change of position, air cushion and water bed etc. A hip fracture in elderly patients is a known high-risk factor for development of pressure sores. Versluysen [22] reported an incidence of 32% overall in elderly patients who were admitted for elective hip surgery or management of proximal femoral fractures. Of

these, 17% were present on admission, and of the remainder, 34% developed sores within the first week and a further 24% in the second week. S. Haleem et al. [23] reported 3.8% of their study patients developed pressure sores.

Patient factors that increased the risk of pressure sores were increased age, diabetes mellitus, a lower mental test score, a lower mobility score, a higher ASA score, lower admission hemoglobin and an intra-operative drop in blood pressure. Lefaiivre et al. [27] showed that when the surgery was delayed for more than 24 h, it was significantly related to increase in pressure sore. Grimes et al. [28] showed that the risk of decubitus ulcer increased as the surgery was delayed for more than 96 h.

Figure 2: Bed Sore

Duration of Surgery and Amount of Blood Loss

In the uncemented group the mean duration of surgery was 80.66 minutes with a mean amount of blood loss of 226.66 milliliters, where as in the cemented group the mean duration of surgery was 91.53 minutes and mean amount of blood loss being 281.33 milliliters.

Surgical time (91.53 minutes versus 80.66minutes) and blood loss (281.33ml versus 226.66 ml) was greater for the cemented cohort than the uncemented. The difference between the groups

was significant ($P < 0.001$). Wender Figved MD et al. [19] reported duration of 70.2 min with a blood loss of 300ml in uncemented group and 82.6 min with a blood loss of 390ml in the cemented group. Jaimo Ahn MD, PhD, Li-Xing Man MD et al. [21] in their study recorded two operative parameters of blood loss and surgical time was lower for the uncemented cohorts. The weighted average blood loss was 476 mL for the cemented and 338 mL for the uncemented groups. Surgical time was greater for the cemented cohort than the uncemented (95 minutes versus 80 minutes, respectively).

Table 6: Showing mean amount of blood loss and mean duration of surgery in the comparable clinical studies

Clinical Studies	Mean Amount Of Blood Loss (in ml)		Mean Duration Of Surgery (in mins)	
	Uncemented	Cemented	Uncemented	Cemented
Our study	226.66	281.33	80.66	91.53
Wender Figved MD et.al,	300	390	70.2	82.6
Jaimo Ahn MD, PhD, Li-Xing Man MD et.al,	338	476	80	95

Pain Assessment using Visual Analogue Score (VAS)

In our study, the mean Visual Analogue Score at 2 weeks for the uncemented group was 3.466 and for the cemented group were 3.133. This was not statistically significant. (P=0.199) The mean Visual Analogue Score at 6 weeks for the uncemented group was 3.2 and for the cemented group were 2.8. This was statistically significant. (P=0.013) The mean Visual Analogue Score at 6 months for the uncemented group was 2.46 and for the cemented group was 1.866.

This was statistically significant. (P=0.004) The results of this study is comparable to the study by Kapoor U et al. [24] where they report a VAS of 2.9 for the uncemented group and 2.1 for the cemented group at the end of 6 months. Chaurasia T et al. [25] reported a VAS of 2.6 for the uncemented group and 1.8 for the cemented group at the end of 12 months.

Mean Harris Hip Score

The mean Harris Hip Score at 2 weeks for the uncemented group was 64.6 and for the cemented group were 66.66. This was not statistically significant. (P=0.123). The mean Harris Hip Score at 6 weeks for the uncemented group was 74.73 and for the cemented group were 75.06. This was not statistically significant. (P=0.88). The mean Harris Hip Score at 6 months for the uncemented group was 84.86 and for the cemented group were 86.13. This was not statistically significant. (P=0.533).

Although the Cemented group had a better Harris Hip Score at the end of 2weeks, 6 weeks and 6 months, there was no statistical significance to the results. Chaurasia et al. [25] reported a mean Harris Hip Score of 83.1 in their study and concluded that the patients benefited from a cemented method. Singh H et al. [26] reported no statistical significance between the mean Harris Hip Score between the uncemented and cemented group at the end of 6weeks, 12 weeks and 6 months. Wender Figved et al. [19] reported equivalence between the groups, with 70.9 in the cemented group and 72.1 in the uncemented group after 3 months (mean difference, 1.2) and 78.9 and 79.8 after 12 months (mean difference, 0.9).

In our study at the end of 6 months, the uncemented group had 4 (26.66%) patients had

Excellent outcome, 9(60%) patients had good outcome and 2(13.3%) patients had Fair outcome.

In the cemented group, 5(33.33%) patients had Excellent outcome, 9(60%) patients had good outcome and 1(6.66) patient had a poor outcome. Kapoor U et al. [24] reported similar results with majority of patients with a Good Outcome in both cemented and uncemented groups.

These results are comparable to the study by Singh H et al. [26] where they reported 35.71% excellent results, 51.92% good results and 12.37% fair results. Anderson et al. [28] they reported 51.9% excellent results, 28.4% good results, 14.8% fair results and 4.9% poor results.

Conclusion

- Fracture neck of femur is a geriatric disease more common in elderly females.
- Surgical time is significantly lower in uncemented bipolar hemiarthroplasty.
- Intra operative Blood loss is comparably more in cemented bipolar hemiarthroplasty.
- Pain was comparably lower in cemented bipolar hemiarthroplasty.
- There is no statistically significant difference in the functional outcome between cemented and uncemented bipolar hemiarthroplasty.
- With a larger sample size and a longer duration of follow up, the recommendation would have been more specific.
- Both cemented and uncemented bipolar hemiarthroplasties are good treatment options for treatment of displaced femoral neck fractures in elderly

References

1. Bhandari M, Devereaux PJ, Tornetta P 3rd, Swiontkowski MF, Berry DJ, Haidukewych G, Schemitsch EH, Hanson BP, Koval K, Dirschl D, Leece P, Keel M, Petrisor B, Heetveld M, Guyatt GH. Operative management of displaced femoral neck fractures in elderly patients: an international survey. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 2005; 87: 2122–2130.
2. Parker MJ, Gurusamy K. Arthroplasties (with and without bone cement) for proximal femoral fractures in adults. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2006; 3: CD001706.
3. Parvizi J, Holiday AD, Ereth MH, Lewallen DG. The Frank Stinchfield Award. *Sudden*

- death during primary hip arthroplasty. *Clin Orthop* 1999; 369: 39-48.
4. Yusuf ozturkmen, Mahmut Karamemetoglu, Mustafa Caniklioglu, Yener Ince, Ibrahim Azboy. Cementless hemiarthroplasty for femoral neck fractures. *IJO- january-march 2008/ volume42/Issue 1*
 5. Wender Figved MD, Vidar Opland MD, Frede Frihagen MD, Tore Jervidalo MD, Jan Erick Madsen MD, PhD, Lars Nordsletten MD, PhD. Cemented versus Uncemented Hemiarthroplasty for Displaced Femoral Neck Fractures *Neck Fractures: The Association of Bone and Joint Surgeons (2009) 467:2426-2435.*
 6. Parker MJ: Fractures of the neck of the femur. *Trauma*.2008; 10(1):43-53.
 7. Donaldson AJ, Thomson HE, Harper NJ, Kenny NW: Bone cement implantation syndrome. *Br J Anaesth*. 2009; 102(1):12.
 8. Choudhary and Mohite. Pathology of fracture neck of femur. *Clinical Orthopaedics India*1987; Vol 1:45-48
 9. Austin T. Moore: The self-locking metallic hip prosthesis. *JBJS* 1957; 39A: 811-27.
 10. Brown J.T. and AbramiG. Transcervical femoral fractures. *JBJS* 1964;46B: 648- 663
 11. Evarts C.M. Endoprosthesis as the primary treatment of femoral neck fractures. *Clinc. Orthop*.1973; 92: 69-76.
 12. Hinchey and Day. Primary prosthetic replacement in fresh femoral neck Fractures. *JBJS*1960; 42B: 633-640.
 13. Ingalhalikar V.T. Shekar Kumta. Fracture neck femur anatomical and biomechanical aspects. *Clinc. Orthop*. India 1987.
 14. Seth M.K. (Col). Stress fractures of the neck of femur. *Clinical Orthopaedics India*1987; Vol 1: 105-109.
 15. Stevens J., Freeman P.A., Nordin B.E.C. and Barnett E. The incidence of osteoporosis in patients with femoral neck fractures *JBJS* 1962;44B: 520-527
 16. Hinchey and Day. Primary prosthetic replacement in fresh femoral neck Fractures. *JBJS*1960; 42B: 633-640.
 17. Khan RJ, MacDowell A, Crossman P, Datta A, Jallali N, Arch BN, Keene GS. Cemented or uncemented hemiarthroplasty for displaced intracapsular femoral neck fractures. *Int Orthop*. 2002;26:229-232
 18. Foster AP, Thompson NW, Wong J, Charlwood AP: Periprosthetic femoral fractures--a comparison between cemented and uncemented hemiarthroplasties. *Injury*. 2005;36(3):424-429
 19. Wender Figved MD, Vidar Opland MD, Frede Frihagen MD, Tore Jervidalo MD, Jan Erik Madsen MD, PhD, Lars Nordsletten MD, PhD *Clin Orthop Relat Res (2009) 467:2426-2435*
 20. S Jameson, P James, A Rangan, S Muller, and M Reed; Cemented versus uncemented hemiarthroplasty for intracapsular fractured neck of femur - a national analysis of matched NHS patients; *J Bone Joint Surg Br Proceedings* 2012 94-B:29
 21. Jaimo Ahn MD, PhD, Li-Xing Man MD, MSc, SangDo Park MD, Jeffrey F. Sodl MD, Systematic Review of Cemented and Uncemented Hemiarthroplasty Outcomes for Femoral Neck Fractures, *Clin Orthop Relat Res (2008) 466:2513- 2518*
 22. Margaret Versluysen; How elderly patients with femoral fracture develop pressure sores in hospital *British Medical Journal* Volume 292
 23. S. Haleem, G. Heinert, M.J. Parker Pressure sores and hip fractures *Injury* Volume 39, Issue 2, February 2008, Pages 219-223
 24. Kapoor U, Chugh A, Baranwal G, Patil S, Kumar S. Comparing outcomes in cemented vs uncemented hemiarthroplasty in femoral neck fractures. *Int J Res Orthop* 2019; 5:152-5.
 25. Chaurasia T, Charan R. Cemented versus uncemented hemiarthroplasty in elderly patients with displaced femoral neck fractures. *Int J Res Orthop* 2018; 4:519-22.
 26. Singh H, Rudani TS, Gandhi MP, Rampurwala AJ. Comparison of functional outcomes between cemented and uncemented bipolar hemiarthroplasty for intracapsular neck femur fractures. *Int J Res Orthop* 2020; 6:333-9.
 27. Lefavre KA, Macadam SA, Davidson DJ, Gandhi R, Chan H, Broekhuyse HM (2009) Length of stay, mortality, morbidity and delay to surgery in hip fractures. *J Bone Joint Surg Br* 91 (7):922-927
 28. Grimes JP, Gregory PM, Noveck H, Butler MS, Carson JL (2002) the effects of time-to-surgery on mortality and morbidity in patients following hip fracture. *Am J Med* 112(9):702-709.